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Techno-economical assessment of vehicle-to-grid in a microgrid: Case study

Gilles Van Kriekinge^{1,2}, Cedric De Cauwer^{1,2}, Joeri Van Mierlo^{1,2}, Thierry Coosemans^{1,2},
Maarten Messagie^{1,2}

¹*ETEC department & MOBI Research Group, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), Pleinlaan 2, 1050 Brussel, Belgium
(E-mail: givkriek@vub.be)*

²*Flanders Make, 3001 Heverlee, Belgium*

Summary

Vehicle-to-grid is a promising solution to help integrate renewable energy sources into the electricity grid. This study focuses on microgrids using long-term parking lots and assesses the economical impact of changing an existing parking lot with internal combustion cars to a parking lot with electric vehicles and bi-directional chargers. In addition, it answers the questions on how many chargers should be installed and at what power. In order to fulfill this task, an energy management system, a parking pattern and a control strategy are developed and simulated. The results show that several parameters have strong impacts on an economical aspect for the microgrid's owner, such as the price of the chargers, the available capacity per car and the price of electricity.

Keywords: Vehicle-to-grid, long-term parking, charging strategies, economical assessment, bi-directional chargers

1 Introduction

Climate change becomes an important concern for humans nowadays, and is caused by greenhouse gasses emitted by human activities. 41% of the total CO_2 emissions results from the electricity-heat sector and 24% by the transport sector [1]. The two combined produce around two thirds of the total carbon dioxide emissions. In order to decrease the emissions of each sector, renewable energy sources (RES) and electric vehicles (EVs) are two promising solutions to reduce them.

Renewable energy sources become a serious alternative to conventional power plants. Among these RES, the installed capacity of solar and wind energy increase massively [2]. However, their availability is not constant, which results, for instance, in new solutions such as energy storage systems in microgrids [3]. Microgrids, which are also called local energy systems (LES), aim to optimize the energy system at a smaller scale compared to the grid, in order to decrease exchange of power with the grid. The electric vehicle is a new alternative to thermal cars, being less pollutant. Even if EVs have many advantages, some important issues have to be solved, such as an important impact on the grid with higher peak demand, higher electricity demand and CO_2 emissions highly depended on the electricity mix used [4], [5]. To overcome these issues, smart charging and bi-directional charging are introduced as two promising solutions.

Nowadays, vehicle-to-grid (V2G), is a widely discussed topic in scientific literature and appears as the new charging method for electric vehicles (EVs) [6]. The goal is to use the batteries of EVs as a service for the grid when the cars are not used for travel. Several types of services exist: frequency control, reactive power compensation, peak load shifting, peak load shaving, storage services for renewable energies, etc [7]. Among the possible services offered by V2G, this paper will focus on the integration of renewable energy sources in a microgrid by using EV's batteries as an energy storage system. In literature, few studies focus on microgrids with long-term parking lots. If these vehicles are replaced by EVs, a new opportunity opens up for V2G. This study investigates the number of bi-directional chargers and the associated power needed, in the case of a microgrid with a long-term parking lot, and studies the impact on the electricity prices. In other words, the research focuses on the economical impact of going from thermal car parking lot to electric cars, by installing bi-directional chargers.

2 Methodology

The model is based on an existing microgrid in Belgium. It consists of 1251 kW_p of solar panels and a 520 kW_{pe} combined heat and power (CHP) generation unit. The microgrid has a parking lot with thermal cars which may be replaced by electric vehicles in the coming years. The goal is to include these EVs as a storage system in the microgrid. In order to fulfill this task, a parking pattern and a charging strategy are needed.

In a first step, an energy management strategy (EMS) is developed for a stationary energy storage system. In other words, the EVs are simplified into one stationary storage, considered as always available. Several strategies have been created, partly based on [8], and tested on the microgrid model. The strategy having demonstrated the greatest reduction in total cost of ownership (TCO) for the microgrid has been retained to use for the V2G simulation. This strategy is explained in section 3.2.

The model of the microgrid with the parking lot is based on a parking pattern. In order to simulate V2G, it is important to know when the EVs are available, along with their technical characteristics. Most of the studies focuses on mobility patterns for work offices or homes. In this study, the microgrid's mobility pattern is specific to vehicles parked for a long period of time (e.g. multiple days), such as parking lots of airports, train stations or car distributors. This pattern is explained in section 3.3.

To apply the energy management strategy into the model, a charging scheduler is needed in order to distribute the energy among the EVs. The control method of the charging scheduler is based on a centralized control where the microgrid has full control over the EVs, which means that only one actor is deciding how EVs are managed [9]. This control is explained in section 3.4.

The economical aspects and parameters are introduced in section 3.1. They are used in the model, and the results are shown in section 4.

3 Model

3.1 Economical formulas used for techno-economical assessment

In order to perform a feasibility study, two specific parameters are used: the total cost of ownership (TCO) and the annual return on investment (AROI). The TCO is a calculation method used to compare more comprehensively different investments, taking into account both capital and operating costs. Its formula is shown in equation 1 [10].

$$TCO = I_0 - RV + \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{AOC}{(1+s)^t} \quad (1)$$

I_0 is the initial investment of the bi-directional chargers [euros], RV is the resale value at present value [euros], N is the lifetime of the investment [years], AOC is the annual operating cost [euros] which is discounted with a discount rate s . In this study, it is assumed that the RV is zero, the discount rate is 2% [11] and that the AOC represents only the electricity invoices.

Nevertheless, two different investments could have the same TCO. The raised question is which of the two investments has the highest economical value. The return-on-investment (ROI) or the annual return-on-investment (AROI) answer this question. The ROI and AROI are shown in equation 2 and 3.

$$ROI = \frac{\text{Investment gain}}{\text{Investment base}} \quad (2)$$

$$AROI = ROI^{\frac{1}{N}} - 1 \quad (3)$$

3.2 The energy management strategy

The energy management strategy is a ruled-based algorithm which makes (dis-)charging decision every 15 minutes. The EMS has been developed based on data from the generation units and the analysis of the 2016's load schedule on a 15 minutes basis. From this analysis, two main distinctions have been set:

1. A distinction between working days and weekends.
2. A distinction between summer, winter and interseason.

The first distinction, between working days and weekends, is done because of the price of electricity and the load demand. During the working days, there are two different prices: On-peak hours, which take place during the day between 7am and 10pm, and off-peak hours, which take place during the night between 10pm and 7am. During the weekend, the price is fixed to off-peak hours. Table 1 shows the price of the electricity used in the simulation, which is based on the actual price of the market in this case study. In addition, the load demand is higher during the working days than during the weekend.

Table 1: Price of electricity

	Injection prices (€/kWh)	Supply prices (€/kWh)
On-peak	-0.035	0.128
Off-peak	-0.029	0.110

The second distinction, between seasons, is done because of strong seasonal variation of PV and CHP production. For instance, the production of heat via the CHP will be higher during the winter than the summer. On the contrary, the production of electricity via the PV will be higher during the summer. In addition, the CHP heat production is lower during the weekend than during the working days.

The ruled-based algorithm is shown in figure 1. During the periods of overproduction, the algorithm will charge the EVs (if possible) to avoid injection to the grid which has to be avoided for economical reasons. On the contrary, during the periods of underproduction, depending on the period considered, one of the six sub-strategies will take on.

Figure 1: Flowchart of the energy management strategy

The differences between the sub-strategies are based on the grid prices, the PV production, the CHP production and the load demand. The general principle of sub-strategies A, B, C is explained as follow: the goal is to avoid buying electricity during on-peak hours, and at the same time to avoid selling electricity back to grid. So the strategy will fully charge the battery before 7am, then discharge it (if needed) to reduce peak demand in the morning, then to charge it again if there is overproduction, and finally discharge it during peak demand in the afternoon. The rate of (dis)-charging varies between each sub-strategy.

The general working of sub-strategies D, E, F is explained as follow: the weekend is an off-peak period where the price is thus the same from Friday 10 pm until Monday 7 am. This means that the only way to pay less, is to discharge the battery when there is underproduction, and charge it when there is overproduction. The strategy is simply to take a small risk to discharge the battery before overproduction in order to have a depleted battery for the overproduction period. The idea behind this strategy is to avoid injection as much as possible. The rate of (dis)-charging varies between each sub-strategy.

3.3 Microgrid's mobility pattern

One of the specific characteristic of this paper is to analyse long-term parking lots where cars stay more than one day parked. In this paper, the case study is based on a parking lot of a car distributor in Belgium. The capacity of it is 7500 cars, where a part of them stay between two and three months before being sold to dealers. From this, it can be assumed that the chargers will be always connected to a car.

The mobility pattern is also influenced by the technical characteristics of the EVs. Since there are no EVs yet on the parking, the technical characteristics of the EVs on the parking have been randomly chosen from today's EV characteristics: capacity of the EV, (dis)-charging power and (dis)-charging efficiency. The state-of-charge (SOC) of the EVs at the beginning of the stay is randomly chosen. An additional rule has been added, which is to set the SOC to 100% before it is sold to a dealer.

3.4 Control of the electric vehicles

The EMS, presented in section 3.2, gives the amount of energy to charge or to discharge the EVs. This amount of energy needs to be individually distributed among the EVs. Since the EVs are not yet sold to their owners, a centralized control is suitable to distribute the energy.

The EMS has to take into account the charge cycles of the EVs, in order to take into account the lifetime of the batteries. To avoid unfair charge cycles between the EVs, the algorithm works as follow: it will seek for the EV with the lowest cycles, then it will (dis)-charge it and go to the next car with lowest cycles, etc. A detailed flowchart is shown in figure 2 for the case of excess of energy available. The cycles are counted from the first day the car is parked, so it does not take into account previous cycle.

Figure 2: Flowchart for the controlling of EVs

4 Simulation results

The question addressed in this study is how many chargers should be installed and at what power, in order to have an economically viable investment. Three different bi-directional chargers have been simulated, with the associated cost. For the cost, two different scenarios are simulated: a current market price scenario and a future market price scenario with an expected reduction of 40% in price. The characteristics are summarised in Table 2. The prices are based on a market analysis on charging infrastructures.

Table 2: Price and power of bi-directional chargers

	Type	Power (kW)	Current market prices (euros)	Future market prices (euros)
Charger 1	AC	3,7	1850	1110
Charger 2	AC	7,4	3700	2220
Charger 3	DC	10	9500	5700

4.1 Base case scenario

For the base case scenario, the following assumptions have been chosen :

- The days of stay of the EVs is expected to be between 60 days and 90 days, as mentioned by the microgrid owner, and which is thus specific to this case study.
- Minimum SOC of 45% and maximum SOC of 55%. As mention in [12], for battery health reason, it is better to cycle close to a SOC of 50%.
- Capacity of EVs of minimum 40 kWh and maximum 90 kWh, and a charging/discharging efficiency of 95%. These values are based on the current characteristics of the EVs on the market.

The TCO for the microgrid's owner is shown in figure 3. The three chargers are shown for the case of the current market prices.

Figure 3: Base case, TCO in function of number of chargers, for the three different chargers

With this basic case, it can be observed that AC chargers are economically more interesting compared to DC chargers. This is explained by the fact that AC chargers have a lower initial cost, but it is also explained by the fact that high power chargers are not necessarily needed. In other words, two factors have an impact and are mentioned below:

- A lower initial cost induces a lower TCO for the microgrid's owner.
- A lower initial cost induces the possibility to add more chargers, and thus to have more EVs connected. The more EVs there are, the more available capacity there is for the microgrid.

To understand this, two specific examples are explained: 30 chargers of 3.7kW and 15 chargers of 7.4kW. The available maximum power is 111kW, and the investment cost is 55500 euros for both cases. However, as shown in figure 3, the final TCO is lower for 3.7kW chargers than 7.4kW chargers. This can be explained by the fact that with 30 3.7kW chargers, there are more EVs, hence more aggregated capacity available for the EMS to balance supply and demand at favorable times.

4.2 Sensitivity analysis on the price of the chargers

This sensitivity analysis takes into account the future market price scenario, and compared it with the current market price scenario. The TCO is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: TCO in function of number of chargers, for different charger prices

The future market price scenario shows logically the best results, and the optimal solution is built with 50 AC V2G chargers with a power of 3.7kW. On the other hand, the DC charger is still not economically viable. Similar to figure 4, figure 5 shows the AROI per type of charger and for both scenarios. If the future market price scenario is taken into account, figure 5 shows that 7.4kW AC chargers can be economically viable, and for a low amount of chargers, it could even be better than 3.7kW AC chargers with current market prices.

Figure 5: AROI in function of number of chargers, for different charger prices

4.3 Sensitivity analysis on available capacity per car

Previous results indicate that low power chargers have better results, however, if the available capacity per EV changes, the results might change. In order to avoid too many results in one graph, only the future market price scenario will be simulated. Two additional ranges of SOC are simulated: 40-60% and 47-53%. The TCO is shown in figure 6 with each time a subplot representing one of the three chargers. The color code is the same as in the previous figures.

Figure 6: TCO in function of number of chargers, for different range of SOC

As expected, the more available capacity there is per EV, the lower the TCO, hence the higher the economical gain is for the microgrid's owner. The impact of the SOC range is considerable on the TCO so it is definitely an important parameter to take into account. Figure 6 shows that 10kW DC chargers could become economically viable, but with low values compared to other chargers. On the other hand, as a secondary effect, the greater the SOC range is, the higher the degradation of the battery will be. However, the battery degradation is not taken into account in this simulation. The reason is that the EVs stay less than three months on the parking lot before sold to the owners, leading to a low cycle aging.

4.4 Sensitivity analysis on price of electricity

Two main parameters have an impact on the TCO which are the investment of the chargers, and the electricity prices. The goal of this section is to assess the impact of the second parameter by changing the price of the electricity. Two main scenarios are tested: a first scenario assesses the impact of a higher difference between on- and off-peak prices by increasing on-peak hour tariff by 20%, and a second scenario which assesses the impact on a 20% increase on all the electricity prices introduced in table 1.

To avoid too many results on one graph, only the future market price scenario will be studied. On the left side of figure 7, the increase of 20% on the on-peak hour price is shown. On the right, a 20% on the overall price of electricity is applied.

Figure 7: Sensitivity analysis on the available SOC, from low power chargers to higher power

It can be observed that the price of the electricity has a real impact on the AROI. As shown on the left, a bigger difference between on-peak and off-peak hours induces a major increase in AROI. For instance, for 30 chargers and for the basic scenario, the AROI is close to 2%. If a higher on-peak price scenario is taken into account, the AROI increases up to 6%. This shows that the EMS used is effective, since it decreases mainly the supply of electricity (including on-peak hours supply), so decreasing the electricity invoices, hence the TCO.

On the other hand, increasing all electricity prices (on/off peak and supply/injection) at once, has also a big impact, but lower than the previous case. By taking the previous example, the AROI for the higher price scenario is now close to 5.5 %. It is due to the EMS that buys electricity during the night, at a higher price in this scenario.

5 Conclusion

This paper presented an economical study on vehicle-to-grid applied on a specific microgrid, where EVs stay between two and three months parked and connected to the microgrid. Several charger powers have been simulated, and the main conclusion is that lower power bi-directional chargers have a greater decrease in TCO for the microgrid's owner than high power bi-directional chargers. For current market price scenario, the best configuration is build with 30 3.7 kW AC bi-directional chargers. The main reason to go for lower power chargers is because higher power chargers are more expensive, but also because it is more important to have many EVs connected. Indeed, the more EVs are connected, the more capacity there is for the EMS. In other words, the aggregated capacity has a bigger impact than the aggregated power.

This study also showed that the price of the electricity, the available capacity per car and the price of the chargers have significant impact on the economical results. Lower price for bi-directional chargers will decrease the TCO for the microgrid's owner, leading to an economical interest in 7.4kW chargers. However, most of the bi-directional chargers in the market are 10 kW DC. These chargers could become economically viable only if the available capacity per EV is greater than the basic scenario. The results show that if more than 10% of the capacity of the EV is used, then DC chargers become economically viable for the microgrids owner. However, the impact on the battery health could become greater, hence a negative impact for the future EV owners. Finally, if the price of the electricity increases by 20 % (for both scenarios), the AROI for the investment of 30 bi-directional chargers increase by 3.5 % to 4 %.

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References

- [1] IEA, “CO2 emissions from fuel combustion 2019 Overview,” *International Energy Agency*, 2019.
- [2] —, “World Energy Outlook 2019,” *International Energy Agency*, 2019.
- [3] R. Wang, P. Wang, and G. Xiao, *Intelligent microgrid management and EV control under uncertainties in smart grid*, 2017.
- [4] M. H. Ö.-I. e.V. Peter Kasten, Joß Bracker, “Assessing the status of electrification of road transport passenger vehicles and potential future implications for the environment and European energy system,” Tech. Rep., 2016.
- [5] M. Messagie, F. S. Boureima, T. Coosemans, C. Macharis, and J. V. Mierlo, “A range-based vehicle life cycle assessment incorporating variability in the environmental assessment of different vehicle technologies and fuels,” *Energies*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1467–1482, 2014.
- [6] J. Hildermeier, C. Kolokathis, J. Rosenow, M. Hogan, C. Wiese, and A. Jahn, “Integrating EVs into the grid : A global review of promising practices,” *EVS32 Symposium*, pp. 1–12, 2019.
- [7] S. Rangaraju, *Environmental performance of battery electric vehicles – Implications for future integrated electricity and transport system*, 2018.
- [8] D. Thomas, O. Deblecker, and C. S. Ioakimidis, “Optimal operation of an energy management system for a grid-connected smart building considering photovoltaics’ uncertainty and stochastic electric vehicles’ driving schedule,” *Applied Energy*, vol. 210, pp. 1188–1206, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.07.035>
- [9] J. Hu, H. Morais, T. Sousa, and M. Lind, “Electric vehicle fleet management in smart grids: A review of services, optimization and control aspects,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 56, pp. 1207–1226, apr 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032115013970?via%3Dihub>
- [10] C. G. Hoehne and M. V. Chester, “Optimizing plug-in electric vehicle and vehicle-to-grid charge scheduling to minimize carbon emissions,” *Energy*, vol. 115, pp. 646 – 657, 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544216312981>
- [11] “Reference and discount rates since 01.08.1997,” 2019. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/competition/state_aid/legislation/reference_rates.html
- [12] A. W. Thompson, “Economic implications of lithium ion battery degradation for vehicle-to-grid (v2x) services,” *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 396, pp. 691 – 709, 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378775318306499>

Authors

Gilles Van Kriekinghe obtained his Master's Degree in Electromechanical engineering at the Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB) in 2019, with a specialisation in energy. His master thesis is about a techno-economic assessment of the integration of solar energy, storage system and vehicle-to-grid technology in a microgrid. He is now working on "Optimized bi-directional & smart vehicle charging in local energy systems (OPTIBIDS)".